

Rest-to-Rest Trajectory Planning of a Flexible Robot Link with Elastic Joint

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Abstract—A method is presented for planning a rest-to-rest motion in given time and with zero final vibration for a one-link flexible robot with an elastic joint. We combine in the dynamic model a finite-dimensional description of the flexible link with the transmission elasticity between motor and link. A flat output having no zero dynamics is defined for the system and a suitable smooth trajectory is designed for the task. The nominal torque is then obtained by inverse dynamics.

Index Terms—Link flexibility, elastic joint, rest-to-rest motion

I. INTRODUCTION

The two primary sources of vibrations in lightweight robots are link and transmission flexibility. Link flexibility is distributed in nature, but can be modeled as an Euler-Bernoulli beam with dynamic boundary conditions, using a finite number of exact shape eigenfunctions and associated eigenfrequencies [1]. Transmission flexibility is usually modeled as a concentrated effect with an elastic spring at the joint [2]. Since the two phenomena interact and link mode shapes are also affected by the elasticity at the joint, they must be considered together for an accurate dynamic modeling [3].

Various control methods exist separately for the two classes of robots with link flexibility or with joint elasticity, but they are rarely combined together [2]. We consider here the control task of moving the flexible robot arm between two undeformed equilibrium configuration in an arbitrary given time. For a flexible link, this problem has been solved using input shaping [4] or by defining an output with no zero dynamics (flat) and then applying an inverse dynamics to a suitably planned trajectory [5]. In this paper, we show that the latter approach can be extended also to the complete dynamic model of a one-link flexible robot with an elastic joint.

II. DYNAMIC MODEL

A one-link flexible robot moving on the horizontal plane is composed by a motor, an elastic transmission and a flexible link. The motor produces a torque τ , has a rotor of inertia I_R , and drives through an elastic spring of stiffness k the flexible link, which is a beam of length l , uniform linear density ρ , Young modulus E , and moment of inertia of the cross section I . The link undergoes small bending deflections only in the plane of motion and satisfies the Euler-Bernoulli beam modeling assumptions [1]. We define a moving frame (x, y, z) attached to the rotor, making an angle θ with respect

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Fig. 1: A flexible link with an elastic transmission at the joint. to the fixed reference frame (x_0, y_0, z_0) (with $z \equiv z_0$). This moving frame is used to describe the arm deformation as a transversal bending $w(x, t)$, which is due both to the transmission elasticity at the joint and to the flexibility of the link. The angular position of the tip is characterized by the angle α_P pointing at it (see Fig. 1).

Using Hamilton principle as in [3], the dynamic model is given by an ordinary and a partial differential equation

$$I_T \ddot{\theta}(t) + \rho \int_0^l x \ddot{w}(x, t) dx = \tau(t) \quad (1)$$

$$EI w''''(x, t) + \rho(\ddot{w}(x, t) + x \ddot{\theta}(t)) = 0, \quad (2)$$

with boundary conditions at the two link ends

$$\begin{aligned} w(0, t) &= 0 & EI w''(0, t) &= k w'(0, t) \\ w''(l, t) &= 0 & w'''(l, t) &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

where $I_T = I_R + \rho l^3/3$, a prime ($'$) denotes a spatial derivative with respect to x , and the dependence of variables on space x and time t is made explicit. We note that one could also add a hub of inertia at the base of the flexible link and a payload at the tip, with mass and inertia. The boundary conditions would change and the dynamic terms would become more complex, but the structure of the dynamic model would remain the same.

The transversal bending $w(x, t)$ can be separated in space and time and expressed as a sum of n mode shapes $\phi_i(x)$ with associated deformations $\delta_i(t)$:

$$w(x, t) = \sum_{i=1}^n \phi_i(x) \delta_i(t).$$

As a result, eqs. (1)-(2) become

$$I_T \ddot{\theta} + \sum_{i=1}^n r_i \ddot{\delta}_i = \tau \quad (3)$$

$$EI \sum_{i=1}^n \phi_i'''' \delta_i + \rho \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \phi_i \ddot{\delta}_i + x \ddot{\theta} \right) = 0, \quad (4)$$

with spatial boundary conditions

$$\phi_i(0) = 0 \quad \phi_i'(0) = \frac{EI}{k} \phi_i''(0) \quad \phi_i''(l) = 0 \quad \phi_i'''(l) = 0,$$

and where

$$r_i = \rho \int_0^l x \phi_i(x) dx, \quad i = 1, \dots, n.$$

Equation (4) can be solved by separation of variables. The equation in space is used to define any number of mode shapes (eigenvectors ϕ_i of a self-adjoint problem, with associated angular eigenfrequencies ω_i , for $i = 1, \dots, n$, as discrete roots of a transcendental characteristic equation), while the time equations can be reformulated as

$$\ddot{\delta}_i + \omega_i^2 \delta_i = -r_i \ddot{\theta}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n. \quad (5)$$

With the configuration

$$\mathbf{q} = (\theta \ \delta_1 \ \delta_2 \ \dots \ \delta_n)^T = (\theta \ \boldsymbol{\delta}^T)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1},$$

the finite-dimensional dynamic model (3), (5) is rewritten as

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{b}\tau \quad (6)$$

with

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} I_T & r_1 & r_2 & \dots & r_n \\ r_1 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ r_2 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_n & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \mathbf{b} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{0}^T \\ \mathbf{0} & \bar{\mathbf{K}} \end{pmatrix} \quad \bar{\mathbf{K}} = \text{diag}\{\omega_1^2 \ \omega_2^2 \ \dots \ \omega_n^2\}.$$

III. REST-TO-REST MOTION DESIGN

Following the procedure in [5], we define a generic (normalized) output function as

$$\mathbf{y} = (1 \ c_1 \ c_2 \ \dots \ c_n) \mathbf{q} = (1 \ \bar{\mathbf{c}}^T) \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{q} \quad (7)$$

and determine its coefficients so that \mathbf{y} has the maximum possible relative degree ($= 2(n+2)$), i.e., it corresponds to an output with vanishing zero dynamics for the flexible robot system — also called a *flat* output. Thus, we should find the n scalar coefficients c_i such that the first $2n+1$ time derivatives of \mathbf{y} are independent from the torque input τ . The form of a generic *even* output derivative is

$$y^{[2j]} = \frac{d^{2j}y}{dt^{2j}} = (\mathbf{c}^T (\mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K})^{j-1} \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{b}) \tau + (-1)^j \mathbf{c}^T (\mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K})^j \mathbf{q}.$$

For $j = 1$, we have

$$\ddot{y} = (\mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{b}) \tau - \mathbf{c}^T (\mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K}) \mathbf{q}.$$

Thanks to the block structure of \mathbf{M} and its inverse,

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} I_T & \mathbf{r}^T \\ \mathbf{r} & \mathbf{I}_n \end{pmatrix} \quad \mathbf{M}^{-1} = \frac{1}{I_T - \mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{r}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\mathbf{r}^T \\ -\mathbf{r} & I_T \mathbf{I}_n \end{pmatrix},$$

it can be shown that $\mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{b} = 0$ is equivalent to

$$\bar{\mathbf{c}}^T \mathbf{r} = 1. \quad (8)$$

For the fourth derivative ($j = 2$)

$$y^{[4]} = -\mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K} \ddot{\mathbf{q}} = -(\mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{b}) \tau + \mathbf{c}^T (\mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K})^2 \mathbf{q},$$

using eq. (8), the required condition is simplified as

$$\mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{b} = 0 \iff \bar{\mathbf{c}}^T \bar{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{r} = 0. \quad (9)$$

Computing similarly the remaining $n-2$ even output derivatives and zeroing each time the coefficient of τ , we obtain other $n-2$ scalar equations of the form

$$\mathbf{c}^T (\mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K})^{j-1} \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{b} = 0, \quad j = 3, \dots, n. \quad (10)$$

The n conditions (8)–(10) provide a linear system, with a $n \times n$ nonsingular coefficient matrix, that can be solved for $\bar{\mathbf{c}} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ in a unique way. The chosen output and its even derivatives define a new set of coordinates for the flexible robot system

$$\mathbf{z} = (y \ y^{[2]} \ y^{[4]} \ \dots \ y^{[2n]})^T = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{q} \quad (11)$$

with the $(n+1) \times (n+1)$ (invertible) transformation matrix

$$\mathbf{Q} = (\mathbf{c} \ \mathbf{A} \mathbf{c} \ \mathbf{A}^2 \mathbf{c} \ \dots \ \mathbf{A}^n \mathbf{c})^T,$$

where $\mathbf{A} = -\mathbf{K} \mathbf{M}^{-1}$ (being \mathbf{M} symmetric and \mathbf{K} diagonal).

The task for the flexible arm is a rest-to-rest motion from $t = 0$ to $t = T$ between two initial and final (undeformed) equilibrium configurations, respectively $\theta(0) = \theta_i$, $\boldsymbol{\delta}(0) = \mathbf{0}$ and $\theta(T) = \theta_f$, $\boldsymbol{\delta}(T) = \mathbf{0}$, with $\dot{\mathbf{q}}(0) = \dot{\mathbf{q}}(T) = \mathbf{0}$.

This becomes a simple interpolation problem in the transformed coordinates

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{z}(0) \\ \dot{\mathbf{z}}(0) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \theta_i \\ \mathbf{0}_n \\ \mathbf{0}_{n+1} \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{z}(T) \\ \dot{\mathbf{z}}(T) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \theta_f \\ \mathbf{0}_n \\ \mathbf{0}_{n+1} \end{pmatrix},$$

which is simplified by the chained structure with derivatives in the new state (whose dynamics has a canonical controllable form). The problem is solved by defining a desired output trajectory $y_d(t)$ that interpolates θ_i and θ_f and has zero boundary conditions at both ends on the time derivatives up to the order $2n+1$. This can be obtained in many ways, the simplest one is by using a polynomial of degree $4n+3$, conveniently expressed in the (doubly) normalized way

$$y_d(t) = \theta_i + (\theta_f - \theta_i) y_{d,n}(s), \quad s = \frac{t}{T} \in [0, 1].$$

Accordingly, the desired state evolution $(\mathbf{z}_d(t), \dot{\mathbf{z}}_d(t))$ is evaluated in a straightforward way. The design is completed by imposing the desired time profile to $2(n+1)$ -th order derivative of the output. This is obtained by the inverse dynamics solution for the torque

$$\tau_d(t) = \frac{y_d^{[2(n+1)]}(t) - \mathbf{c}^T (-\mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K})^{n+1} \mathbf{Q}^{-1} \mathbf{z}_d(t)}{\mathbf{c}^T (-\mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K})^n \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{b}}, \quad (12)$$

with $t \in [0, T]$ and recalling that $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{Q}^{-1} \mathbf{z}$.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We performed numerical simulations¹ in MATLAB on a flexible arm having the following parameters:

$$\begin{aligned} I_R &= 1 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2 & k &= 100 \text{ Nm/rad} \\ l &= 0.7 \text{ m} & \rho &= 4 \text{ kg/m} & EI &= 0.6 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}^2. \end{aligned}$$

The first $n = 3$ modes were considered. The modal analysis provides the associated angular frequencies

$$\omega_1 = 17.13 \quad \omega_2 = 48.00 \quad \omega_3 = 94.08 \quad [\text{rad/s}],$$

with the model coefficients in (6)

$$\mathbf{r}^T = (r_1 \quad r_2 \quad r_3) = (0.1036 \quad -0.0371 \quad 0.0184).$$

The corresponding coefficients of the designed flat output (7) are found to be

$$\mathbf{c}^T = (1 \quad \bar{\mathbf{c}}^T) = (1 \quad 11.4417 \quad 5.3266 \quad 0.6554).$$

The rest-to-rest motion is from $\theta_i = 0$ to $\theta_f = \pi/2$ rad in a given time $T = 0.5$ s. A polynomial of degree $4n + 3 = 15$ has been used for trajectory planning.

Fig. 2: Inverse dynamics torque τ_d for a rest-to-rest motion

Fig. 3: Output $y = y_d$ and rotor angle θ trajectories

Figure 2 shows the oscillating profile of the torque $\tau_d(t)$ computed by the inverse dynamics formula (12). The initial and final torques are nonzero (to impose also these values to zero, a polynomial of degree 17 could have been used). The amount of ‘bounces’ in the torque changes depending on the motion time and the arm (link and joint) stiffness. The evolution of the output $y(t)$, coincident with $y_d(t)$ in the present nominal case, is shown in Fig. 3, together with the

rotor angle $\theta(t)$. It is apparent that the rotor moves in advance of the output in the first half of the motion and then lags behind in a symmetric way in the second half. Figure 4 shows a stroboscopic view of the planar motion of the flexible arm, with the rotor position superposed at the base (best appreciated in the accompanying video). The maximum lateral bending of the link at the tip, $w(l, t) = l(\alpha_P(t) - \theta(t))$, reaches about 2.5 cm during motion (Fig. 5). All dynamic flexibility effects are strongly emphasized by the presence of a payload at the tip (see again the video).

Fig. 4: Stroboscopic view of the flexible arm motion

Fig. 5: Lateral bending of the link at the tip

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¹The code and a report with additional details can be found in the repository at https://github.com/cybernetic-m/r2r_flexible-link_elastic-joint.